

PREVALENCE OF PLANTAR FASCIITIS AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH HAMSTRING TIGHTNESS IN ADULTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17008010>

Keywords

Plantar Fasciitis, Hamstring Tightness, Musculoskeletal Disorders, Prevalence in Adults, Risk Factors

Article History

Received: 8 July 2025

Accepted: 28 July 2025

Published: 30 Aug 2025

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Abstract

Prevalence of plantar fasciitis and its association with hamstring tightness in early adulthood. Background Plantar fasciitis is a common musculoskeletal condition characterized by pain in the heel and bottom of the foot, often aggravated by prolonged standing or walking. Although various local factors have been studied extensively, less attention has been given to the role of proximal muscle tightness, particularly in the hamstrings, as a contributing factor to plantar heel pain. The aim of this study was to determine the association between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis in individuals aged 20 to 40 years. Methods and material This cross-sectional survey included 383 participants selected through non-probability sampling from hospitals, academic institutions, and the general population in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Individuals with clinically diagnosed unilateral plantar fasciitis and measurable hamstring tightness were included. Data were collected using the Plantar Fasciitis Pain Scale (PFPS) to assess pain intensity and functional impact, and the Active Knee Extension (AKE) test to evaluate hamstring flexibility. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21, and chi-square tests were applied to examine associations between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis severity. Results The results revealed a significant association between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis. Participants with moderate to severe tightness reported higher PFPS scores and greater difficulty in daily activities such as walking, stair climbing, and standing. The most commonly reported pain locations were the heel and toes, particularly during the first steps in the morning. Female participants had a higher prevalence of both plantar fasciitis symptoms and hamstring tightness compared to males, with statistically significant differences observed. The study found a strong association between reduced hamstring flexibility and the severity of plantar fasciitis symptoms. These findings highlight the importance of assessing hamstring tightness in individuals with plantar heel pain

and suggest that flexibility-based interventions should be incorporated into treatment strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Plantar fasciitis is an inflammatory response cause by repetitive motion resulting in micro trauma in foot and heel often affecting plantar fascia. Connective tissue that support arch of foot (Palomo-López, 2018). Plantar fasciitis is referred to as heel spur characterized by burning, aching, tenderness and lancinating pain over plantar. Clinical features of plantar fasciitis include unilateral heal pain and in some cases the presentation is bilateral. It also includes Achilles tendon tightness and tenderness over the medial calcaneal tuberosity which my increase by prolonged standing and toe dorsal flexion. (M. A. Tahririan, 2012).

Increased additional stress forces on anatomical band of plantar fascia results in increased abnormal pronator forces which then ultimately provokes plantar fasciitis (Barrett, 1999).

Plantar fasciitis also known as plantar fasciopathy, heel spur syndrome, heel pain syndrome commonly as the pain occurs locally at insertion of aponeurosis on the calcaneus bone's medial tubercle. In the past it has also been considered that plantar fasciitis is an Inflammatory condition. However, in some cases it manifests as a degenerative process which affects the protein collagen or also appears as degenerative fasciitis in which there is no inflammation (Dyck Jr, 2004).

The exact cause of plantar fasciitis is still unknown and likely multifunctional anatomical causes includes degenerative alteration like arthritis, obesity, heel pad atrophy, inflammatory arthropathy and increasing age. External factors include non-supportive footwear, inadequate medial arch assistance, prolong standing and weight bearing. Some conditions also includes heel spurs, increase introsseous pressure at calcaneus, chronic inflammation, periosteal inflammation, nerve entrapment and micro trauma at fascia.(Lee, (2023). Chronic heel pain includes broad spectrum of different conditions effecting

plantar area of foot including bursitis, neuritis, nerve entrapment, spurs and degenerative changes. These modifications will lead to large joint rotation and decreased joint and increased soft tissue stress forces. I.E quadriceps avoidance gait. This results decreased forces at knee joint while increasing it at plantar surface of foot leading into plantar fasciitis. (Henriksen, 2012). In elderly population, degeneration of fascia is due to degenerative process including circulatory changes, collagen disintegration, surgical biopsy and matrix degeneration. Those degenerative changes have effects on elderly population (Zhang, 2023).

Biceps femoris short head's fascicles originates below the point of distal insertion of gluteus maximus. These usually arise directly from three point (i) from Linea aspera of femur (ii) from upper 2/3 of supracondylar line (iii) laterally from intermuscular septum. Muscle belly is wide, thin and long. It is innervated by common personal nerve (Woodley, 2005)

The hamstring muscles are hip extensors and knee flexors in gait cycles.in swing phase the muscle is active when hip is in extension at last 25% and continue at 50% in swing phase, as the produce extension activity at hip and resist activity at knee. So, when doing partial knee flexion, the muscle bicep femoris rotates the leg externally which is due to its oblique direction (Beltran, 2012).

Hamstring tightness can be defined as a lack of ROM with restriction in posterior thigh musculature, which causes dysfunctional movement of hip.it decreases performance and increases the risk of injury (Hansberger, 2019).

Hamstring mechanical effect on knee and hip joint movement were investigated by the use of dynamic MSK system and findings suggest that the hamstring have capability to increase the function of hip extension. (Frigo, 2010).

Due to tightness in the muscle study reveals that movement pattern changes. Due to effects of

pain during functional activities, a study reveal that pain occur during walking leads to decreased muscle movement in agonistic phase and activity is increased in antagonistic phase. Antagonistic phase. Accordingly, the changes in the gait pattern that occur in bicep femoris during muscle pain (Henriksen, (2011).

There is a role of plantar fasciitis when hamstring tightness occur. As the hamstring tightens they produces excessive load at plantar fascia. All like gastrocnemius tightness, calcaneal spur and hamstring tightness were associated strongly with plantar fasciitis without covariates. After covariates controlling, clients with hamstring tightness experience plantar fasciitis were about 8.7 times (Labovitz JM, 2011).

Previous evidence base practices shows correlation between hamstring tightness and plantar Fasciitis but it also includes secondary factors such as occupation, obesity, disease and trauma etc. As these factors in addition with hamstring tightness leads to inflammation of plantar fascia. Our study solely concern to exclude such factors and determine prevalence between the two, with exclusion of other factors and comorbidity.

Literature Review

A study by Sayed et al. (2019) explored the relationship between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis (PF) in 30 patients aged 31-48 years who presented with heel pain. The researchers used ultrasonography to measure plantar fascia thickness and the Active Knee Extension (AKE) test to assess hamstring length. The results showed a strong negative correlation between plantar fascia thickness and the AKE angle ($r = -0.613$, $p = 0.0001$), suggesting that increased plantar fascia thickness was linked with reduced hamstring flexibility. This finding implies that hamstring tightness may play a role in the development of PF. The authors concluded that addressing hamstring tightness could be helpful in treating PF, although they noted that the study design does not establish a direct causal relationship (MOHAMED A. SAYED, 2019)

A study by Tariq et al. (2024) explored the relationship between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis among runners. The study included 30 athletes diagnosed with plantar fasciitis and assessed hamstring tightness using the Active Knee Extension (AKE) test. The results indicated that 30% of the participants exhibited hamstring tightness. Statistical analysis revealed a moderate negative correlation between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis ($r = -0.48$), with a p-value of 0.068. Although the correlation was not statistically significant, the authors noted that hamstring tightness is common among runners with plantar fasciitis. The study recommended further research to explore other biomechanical factors that may impact plantar fasciitis in athletic population (Tariq, 2024)

A study by KC Sung et al. (2020) investigated the incidence and prevalence of plantar fasciitis in 127,455 nurses as well as 26,024 physicians in nationwide population in Taiwan. From 2006 to 2012 a comparison was done between general population and nurses as well as physicians and general population. In 7 years' time duration about around 8.14% physicians were found to have had incidence of plantar fasciitis and 13.11% nurses were found to have had plantar fasciitis incidence. physicians were at lower risk of plantar fasciitis while nurses had higher risk in comparison with general public. Female physicians were at a greater risk of plantar fasciitis as compared to males. Health promotions events and in occupational work space was recommended for populations which were at risk (Kuo-Chang SUNG, 2020)

Gulrandhe et al. (2023) explored the correlation between hamstring muscle tightness and foot posture in 200 healthy adults. The researchers employed the Foot Posture Index (FPI) and hamstring flexibility assessments. Their results showed a significant relationship between tight hamstrings and pronated foot posture. Since pronation is a known risk factor for plantar fasciitis, the authors suggested a preventative role for hamstring flexibility training.(P Gulrandhe, 2023) Khalil et al. (2022) conducted

a cross-sectional study to assess the prevalence of hamstring tightness and its impact on lower extremity function among asymptomatic individuals with prolonged standing hours. The study involved 65 female nurses, aged between 31 and 35 years, selected through convenient sampling. It was concluded that the prevalence of hamstring tightness in asymptomatic individuals with prolonged standing hours is low (E Khalil, 2022)

Izhar et al. (2023) examined the effectiveness of plantar fascial mobilization and static stretching on hamstring flexibility among overweight individuals. The study included 50 participants divided into intervention and control groups. Results indicated that the intervention group showed significant improvements in hamstring flexibility compared to the control group, highlighting the potential benefits of targeted stretching in managing plantar fasciitis symptoms (Izhar, 2023).

Mohamed et al. (2019) conducted a study to assess the relationship between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis. A study reveals that thirty individuals suffer from heel pain and many have chronic symptoms and went to disability of age 30-35. To assess the thickness of plantar fascia, use ultrasonography and to assess the hamstring length use (AKE) active knee extension aim to detect the relationship between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis. The range was 31 to 48 yrs, from which 83.3 % were female, 66.6% affected bilaterally. This means any increase in plantar fascia thickness causes decrease Active knee extension angle.(MOHAMED A. SAYED, 2019)

Amber et al. (2021) conducted a study to find out association of hamstring tightness with plantar fasciitis in young female runners. Considerable amount of runner's experience hamstring muscle pain due tightness which is the result of tension from plantar fasciitis. They conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study in

which sample size was around 51. A technique called non probability sampling was used in this study. Age group was between 15-to-30-year females. Active knee extension test was used to assess hamstring tightness. From selected sample 51 runners had plantar fasciitis diagnosed through AKET by popliteal angle measurements which gave result of mean (SD) 57.29 (3.83) at affected leg while mean (SD) 1.25(0.44) was found at unaffected leg for plantar fasciitis. Significant amount of association was found between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis in the female runners.(Tariq1 et al., 2021)

Saleh et al. conducted a comparative study to assess hamstring tightness in individuals with and without plantar fasciitis. The study involved a total of 150 participants, divided equally between those diagnosed with plantar fasciitis and a control group without the condition. Hamstring flexibility was evaluated using the Active Knee Extension (AKE) test. The findings revealed that individuals with plantar fasciitis exhibited significantly greater hamstring tightness compared to the control group. It was concluded that hamstring tightness is associated with plantar fasciitis and emphasized the importance of incorporating hamstring stretching exercises in the management and prevention of plantar fasciitis(Sarfraz1 et al., 2023).

Riaz Hashmi et al. (2020) conducted this study, investigated the prevalence of plantar fasciitis among 150 female teachers in Sialkot and its association with age, BMI, footwear type, and standing hours. It found that 46.3% of participants had plantar fasciitis, most commonly affecting the middle sole of the foot. A significant association was observed with increasing age, while BMI, footwear type, and standing duration showed no significant link. The findings highlight age as a key factor in the development of plantar fasciitis.(Hashmi et al., 2020)

MATERIAL & METHODS

Study Design:

The study design of this research is a cross-sectional survey.

Sample Size:

The sample size was calculated using the Open EPI Tool. The calculated sample size was

The screenshot shows the 'Results' tab of the 'Sample Size for Frequency in a Population' calculator. The input parameters are: Population size (N) = 123050, Hypothesized % frequency (p) = 50% +/- 5, Confidence limits as % of 100 (d) = 5%, and Design effect (DEFF) = 1. The resulting sample sizes for various confidence levels are shown in a table below.

Confidence Level (%)	Sample Size
95%	383
80%	165
90%	270
97%	470
99%	660
99.9%	1074
99.99%	1496

The calculator also displays the equation for sample size calculation: $n = [DEFF * N * p(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} * (N-1) + p*(1-p)]$. Below the table, it provides instructions: 'Results from OpenEpi. Version 3. open source calculator--SSPropor. Print from the browser with ctrl-P or select text to copy and paste to other programs.'

Sampling Technique:

Convenient sampling
Study setting:
The selected study was hospitals, general population, universities & institutes

- 2) Presence of hamstring muscle tightness confirmed by clinical assessment
- 3) Pain only on weight bearing upon awakening and after prolong period of sitting

Sample selection:

Subjects who met the inclusion criteria were selected using cross-sectional sampling.
Inclusion Criteria:

- 1) Age between 20 and 40 years
- 4) Time duration of pain 1 month to 6 months
- 5) Plantar fasciitis in adults with unilateral hamstring tightness

Study Duration:

4 months after the approval of synopsis.

Data Collection Procedure:

The purpose of the study was explained to the selected population before data collection.

The study was designed to have no potential physical or emotional harm to participants. All data collected was coded to protect identity and confidentiality, and was not disclosed to anyone.

Tools:

- Plantar Fasciitis Pain Scale (PFPS) questionnaire
- Active Knee Extension Test (AKE)

Statistical Analysis Procedure:

Data was analyzed using SPSS 21.0 IBM Software. Level of significance 0.05 was chosen. Chi square test was used to find association between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis in the dimension of Age, location, depth of pain, and pain in different activities in general population.

Ethical Consideration:

Ethical considerations taken under account in this study included:

1. Informed consent.
2. Ensuring confidentiality was not breached.
3. Avoiding discrimination based on caste, color, or background
4. The study didn't cause any emotional, physical or psychological toll to any participant.

Results and Discussion

Age

Table 1: Age in categories

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	265	69.2	69.2	69.2
	31-40	118	30.8	30.8	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In the population of 383 , 265 participants (69.25%) were of age group 20-30 years and 118 participants (30.8%) lie in age group 31-40 years.

Gender

Table 2: Gender

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	163	42.6	42.6	42.6
	FEMALE	220	57.4	57.4	100.0

Total	383	100.0	100.0
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Out of 383 population 163(42.6%) were male and 220(57.4%) were female.

Visual Analogue Scale

Table 3: Visual analogue scale

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0-2	157	41.0	41.0
	2-4	84	21.9	62.9
	4-6	73	19.1	82.0
	6-8	51	13.3	95.3
	8-10	18	4.7	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0

In population of 383, 157 participants (41%) have VAS score of 0-2, 84 of them (21.9%) have VAS of score 2-4. 73 of them (19.1%) have VAS score 4-6, 51(13.3%) have VAS of 6-8, 18(4.7%) have VAS of 8-10

Frequency of pain in week

Table 4: Frequency of pain in week

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2 times a week	267	69.7	69.7
	4 times a week	55	14.4	84.1
	6 times a week	61	15.9	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0

In 383 population, 267(69.7%) have frequency of pain 2 times in a week, 55 (14.4%) have a pain frequency of 4 times in a week and 61(15.9%) have pain frequency 6 times a week

Depth of pain

Table 5: Depth of pain

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	surface	270	70.5	70.5
	deep	113	29.5	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0

In 383 participants, 270 (70.5%) have pain on surface while 113(29.50%) have pain felt deep.

Location of pain

Table 6: Location of pain

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	toes	158	41.3	41.3	41.3
	ball of foot	51	13.3	13.3	54.6
	mid sole	80	20.9	20.9	75.5
	bottom of heel	94	24.5	24.5	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383 participants, 158 (41.3%) felt pain at toes, 51 (13.3%) have pain located at the ball of foot, 80 (20.9%) at mid sole ,94(24.5%) at bottom of heel.

Frequency of pain in past 6 weeks

Table 7: Frequency of pain in past 6 weeks

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	every other week	179	46.7	46.7	46.7
	once a week	110	28.7	28.7	75.5
	once a day	62	16.2	16.2	91.6
	many times a day	32	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383 people 179(46.74%) have pain felt in every other week, 110(28.72%) have once a week, 62(16.19%) have pain felt once a day and 32(8.36%) have pain frequency many times a day.

Pain free onset

Table 8: Pain free onset

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	weeks	194	50.7	50.7	50.7
	days	72	18.8	18.8	69.5
	hours	67	17.5	17.5	86.9
	minutes	50	13.1	13.1	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In 383 participants 194 (50.7%) have pain free onset in weeks, 72(18.8%) have free onset of pain in days, 67(17.5%) have in hours and 50(13.1%) have in minutes

Duration of pain

Table 9: Duration of pain

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	only when i over exert	219	57.2	57.2	57.2
	pain last for less than one hour	82	21.4	21.4	78.6
	pain last for 1 to 2 hours	36	9.4	9.4	88.0
	pain lasts for more than 2 hours	46	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 219(57.18%) have pain on over exertion, 82(21.4%) have pain last for less than one hour, 36(9.4%) have pain last for 1-2 hours and 46(12%) have pain for more than 2 hours.

Time of day when pain is worst in past 6 weeks

Table 10: Time of day when pain is worst in past 6 weeks

Table 11: Difficulty in sleep due to pain in past 6 weeks

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	227	59.3	59.3	59.3
	some nights	116	30.3	30.3	89.6
	most nights	27	7.0	7.0	96.6
	every night	13	3.4	3.4	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In the population of 383, 227 (59.3%) have no difficulty during sleep, 116(30.3%) have difficulty in sleeping in some nights, 27(7%) have mostly pain in night and 13(3.4%) have sleeping difficulty every night.

Night pain in past 6 weeks

Table 12: Night pain in past 6 weeks

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	253	66.1	66.1	66.1
	some nights	96	25.1	25.1	91.1
	most nights	28	7.3	7.3	98.4

every night	6	1.6	1.6	100.0
Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 253(66.1%) have no pain during night, 96(25.1%) have pain in some nights, 28(7.3%) have pain mostly in night and 6(1.6%) have pain in every night.

Difficulty in pain dealing

Table 13: Difficulty in pain dealing

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	easy to deal with	246	64.2	64.2	64.2
	inconvenient	77	20.1	20.1	84.3
	troublesome	51	13.3	13.3	97.7
	almost impossible	9	2.3	2.3	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383 participants, 246(64.2%) easily deals with pain, 77(20.1%) find it inconvenient to deal, 51(13.3%) have troublesome dealing and 9(2.3%) finds it almost impossible to deal.

Pain interference with walking

Table 14: Pain interference with walking

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	207	54.0	54.0	54.0
	occasionally	117	30.5	30.5	84.6
	frequently	46	12.0	12.0	96.6
	always	13	3.4	3.4	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In 383 population, 207 participants (54%) have no pain interference with walking, 117(30.5%) have occasional pain, 46(12%) have frequent pain and 13(3.4%) always have pain interference with walking.

Time Duration to walk comfortably after awakening

Table 15: Time duration to walk comfortably after awakening

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	no time	225	58.7	58.7	58.7
	less than 10 minutes	40	10.4	10.4	69.2
	11 to 30 minutes	98	25.6	25.6	94.8

it takes over 30 minutes until i can walk	20	5.2	5.2	100.0
Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 225(58.75%) have no pain during walking, 40(10.44%) have less than 10 minutes pain ,98(25.59%) have 11 to 30 minutes duration of pain and 20(5.22%) takes over 30 minutes duration until walk .

Most comfortable is to walk on toes than flat foot

Table 16: Most comfortable is to walk on toes then flat foot

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	no	266	69.5	69.5
	yes	117	30.5	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0

In 383 participants, 266(69.5%) have no occurrence while 117(30.55%) have most comfortable is to walk on toes than flat foot.

Scoring walking in morning

Table 17: Scoring of walking in the morning

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	260	67.9	67.9
	Very little	81	21.1	89.0
	Moderate	34	8.9	97.9
	Severe	8	2.1	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0

Out of 383, 260(67.9%) have no occurrence during walking, 81(21.1%) have very little, 34(8.9%) have moderate during walking and 8(2.1%) have severe pain during walking in morning.

Standing up on your toes

Table 18: Scoring of standing up on your toes

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	213	55.6	55.6
	very little	101	26.4	82.0

Moderate	50	13.1	13.1	95.0
Severe	19	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In 383 population, standing up on your toes have no pain in 213(55.6%), very little in 101(26.4%), moderate in 50(13.1%) while severe score on standing up on your toes in 19 (5%).

Scoring driving

Table 19: Scoring of driving

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	293	76.5	76.5	76.5
	very little	52	13.6	13.6	90.1
	Moderate	26	6.8	6.8	96.9
	severe	12	3.1	3.1	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 293(76.5%) have no pain during driving, 52(13.6%) have very little pain, 26(6.8 %) have moderate pain while in 12 (3.1%) have severe pain during driving.

Climbing Stairs

Table 20: Scoring of climbing stairs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	175	45.7	45.7	45.7
	very little	102	26.6	26.6	72.3
	moderate	69	18.0	18.0	90.3
	Severe	37	9.7	9.7	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383 population, 175 (45.7%) have no pain when climbing stairs, 102 (26.6%) have very little, 69(18%) have moderate while 37 (9.7%) have severe pain during climbing a stairs.

Scoring Descending Stairs

Table 21: Scoring of descending stairs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Not at all	209	54.6	54.6	54.6
	very little	87	22.7	22.7	77.3
	moderate	58	15.1	15.1	92.4
	severe	29	7.6	7.6	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In 383 participants, 209 (54.6%) have no pain, 87(22.7%) have very little pain, 58(15.1%) have moderate and 29(7.6 %) have severe pain in descending stairs.

Reaching Up

Table 22: Scoring of reaching up

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	201	52.5	52.5	52.5
	very little	102	26.6	26.6	79.1
	moderate	54	14.1	14.1	93.2
	severe	26	6.8	6.8	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 201(52.5%) have no pain when reaching up, 102 (26.6 %) have very little, 54(14.1%) have moderate while 26(6.8%) have severe pain.

Bending Over

Table 23: Scoring of bending over

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	204	53.3	53.3	53.3
	very little	111	29.0	29.0	82.2
	moderate	57	14.9	14.9	97.1
	severe	11	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

In population of 383, 204(53.3%) have no pain while bending over, 111(29%) have very little, 57(14.9%) have moderate but 11(2.9%) have severe pain.

4.1.24 Walking bare foot

Table 24: Scoring of walking barefoot

	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Not at all	238	62.1	62.1	62.1
	Very little	86	22.5	22.5	84.6
	Moderate	43	11.2	11.2	95.8
	severe	16	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 238 (62.1 %) have no pain when walking bare foot, 86(22.5 %) have very little, 43(11.2 %) have moderate but 16 (4.2%) have severe pain during barefoot walk.

Standing after watching a movie

Table 25: Scoring of standing after watching a movie

Valid	Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	234	61.1	61.1	61.1
	very little	89	23.2	23.2	84.3
	moderate	46	12.0	12.0	96.3
	severe	14	3.7	3.7	100.0
	Total	383	100.0	100.0	

Out of 383, 234 (61.1%) have no pain, 89(23.2 %) have very little, 46(12%) have moderate but 14(3.7 %) have severe pain when standing after watching a movie.

Associations

Gender and Total score

Gender * Total score Crosstabulation Count

Gender		Total score			Total
		1-30	31-60	60-100	
r	MALE	123	37	3	163
	FEMAL E	133	81	6	220
Total		256	118	9	383

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson ChiSquare	9.525 ^a	2	.009
Likelihood Ratio	9.705	2	.008
N of Valid Cases	383		

a. 1 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.83.

As p-value is <0.05 the two variables have significant association. There is an increase in the prevalence of plantar fasciitis among female population.

Location of pain and walking in the morning

Location of pain * Scoring of walking in the morning Crosstabulation

Count		Scoring Not at all	of walking Very little	in the Moderat e	morning Severe	Total
Location of pain	toes	126	14	16	2	158
	ball of foot	31	13	7	0	51
	mid sole	48	28	2	2	80
	bottom of heel	55	26	9	4	94
Total		260	81	34	8	383

Chi-Square Tests

Asymptotic

Significance

Value(df,2-sided)

Pearson Chi-Square 35.579(9.000)

Likelihood Ratio 39.209(9.000)

N of Valid Cases 383

a. 5 cells (31.3%) have expected count less than

5. The minimum expected count is 1.07.

As p-value is <0.05 indicating significant association between two variables.

There is increase in pain in foot during walking in the morning.

Location of pain and standing up on your toes

Location of pain * Scoring of standing up on your toes Crosstabulation

Count		Scoring Not at all	standing very up on little	Moderat e	your toes Severe	Total
Location of pain	toes	114	22	13	9	158
	ball of foot	23	18	9	1	51
	mid sole	41	25	11	3	80
	bottom of heel	35	36	17	6	94
Total		213	101	50	19	383

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson ChiSquare	38.596 ^a	9	.000
Likelihood Ratio	40.303	9	.000
N of Valid Cases	383		

a. 3 cells (18.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.53.

As p-value is <0.05 showing strong association between two variable. There is an increment of pain while standing on toes.

Gender and hamstring tightness

Gender * Hamstring tightness Crosstabulation Count

		Hamstring 11-20		tightness	Total
		21-30	31-40		
Gender	MALE	89	40	34	163
	FEMALE	101	49	70	220
Total		190	89	104	383

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson ChiSquare	5.774 ^a	2	.056
Likelihood Ratio	5.879	2	.053
N of Valid Cases	383		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 37.88.

As p-value is equal to 0.05 , it shows that there is significant association between two variables. There is increased hamstring tightness among females.

5.1.5 Total score and hamstring tightness

Total score * Hamstring tightness Crosstabulation Count

		Hamstring 11-20		tightness	Total
		21-30	31-40		
Total score	1-30	179	61	16	256
	31-60	11	28	79	118
	60-100	0	0	9	9
Total		190	89	104	383

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	194.110 a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	209.366	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	178.669	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	383		

a. 3 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.09. The p-value is <0.05 , the two variables have significant association. There is an increased total score in participants with hamstring tightness.

Daily life activity limitation due to pain and hamstring tightness

Daily life activity limitations due to pain * Hamstring tightness Crosstabulation
Count

		Hamstring tightness			Total
		11-20	21-30	31-40	
Daily life activity limitations due to pain	does not limit your life style	162	58	47	267
	some activities avoided	27	23	46	96
	you avoid all activity due to injury	1	8	11	20
Total		190	89	104	383

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson ChiSquare	56.169 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	59.314	4	.000
N of Valid Cases	383		

a. 1 cells (11.1%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.65. The p-value is <0.05 , so there is significant association between two variables. There were increased activity limitations due to pain in participants with hamstring tightness.

RESULT

In a total sample of 383 participants, the majority, 265 individuals (69.2%), were in the age group of 20–30 years, while 118 participants (30.8%) were in the 31–40 years age group (Table 1). Regarding gender distribution, there were 163 males (42.6%) and 220 females (57.4%) included in the study (Table 2). Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) scores revealed that 157 participants (41%) had pain levels between 0–2, 84 participants (21.9%) scored between 2–4, 73 participants (19.1%) scored between 4–6, 51 participants (13.3%) scored between 6–8, and 18 participants (4.7%) had pain scores between 8–10 (Table 3). The weekly pain frequency showed that 267 participants (69.7%) experienced pain two times per week, 55 participants (14.4%) reported pain four times per week, and 61 participants (15.9%) experienced pain six times per week (Table 4). Regarding pain depth, 270 participants (70.5%) reported surface-level pain, while 113 participants (29.5%) described their pain as deep (Table 5). As for pain location, 158 participants (41.3%) reported pain in their toes, 51 (13.3%) in the ball of the foot, 80 (20.9%) in the mid-sole, and 94 (24.5%) at the bottom of the heel (Table 6). Concerning pain frequency over the past six weeks, 179 participants (46.7%) felt pain every other week, 110 participants (28.7%) reported pain once per week, 62 participants (16.2%) had pain once per day, and 32 participants (8.4%) reported pain many times per day (Table 7). Pain-free onset was described as weeks by 194 participants (50.7%), days by 72 participants (18.8%), hours by 67 participants (17.5%), and minutes by 50 participants (13.1%) (Table 8). With respect to the duration of pain, 219 participants (57.2%) reported pain only after overexertion, 82 participants (21.4%) experienced pain lasting less than one hour, 36 participants (9.4%) had pain lasting one to two hours, and 46 participants (12%) had pain lasting more than two hours (Table 9). The time of day when pain was worst during the past six weeks showed that 181 participants (47.3%) reported pain consistently throughout the day,

86 (22.5%) in the afternoon only, 67 (17.5%) both day and night, and 49 (12.8%) only upon first getting up (Table 10). Difficulty in sleeping due to pain was reported by 116 participants (30.3%) on some nights, 27 participants (7%) on most nights, and 13 participants (3.4%) every night, whereas 227 participants (59.3%) reported no sleeping difficulty (Table 11). Night pain was not experienced by 253 participants (66.1%), while 96 participants (25.1%) reported pain on some nights, 28 participants (7.3%) on most nights, and 6 participants (1.6%) every night (Table 12).

Regarding the ability to deal with pain, 246 participants (64.2%) found it easy to manage, 77 participants (20.1%) described it as inconvenient, 51 participants (13.3%) found it troublesome, and 9 participants (2.3%) found it almost impossible to manage (Table 13). Pain interference with walking was absent in 207 participants (54%), occasional in 117 participants (30.5%), frequent in 46 participants (12%), and constant in 13 participants (3.4%) (Table 14). When assessing the time to walk comfortably after awakening, 225 participants (58.7%) reported no delay, 40 (10.4%) needed less than 10 minutes, 98 (25.6%) needed 11–30 minutes, and 20 (5.2%) needed more than 30 minutes (Table 15). About 117 participants (30.5%) found it more comfortable to walk on their toes compared to a flat foot, while 266 (69.5%) did not (Table 16). Regarding scoring of walking in the morning, 260 participants (67.9%) reported no pain, 81 participants (21.1%) had very little pain, 34 participants (8.9%) had moderate pain, and 8 participants (2.1%) reported severe pain (Table 17). For standing on toes, 213 participants (55.6%) had no pain, 101 participants (26.4%) had very little pain, 50 participants (13.1%) reported moderate pain, and 19 participants (5%) had severe pain (Table 18). Pain during driving was absent in 293 participants (76.5%), very little in 52 participants (13.6%), moderate in 26 participants (6.8%), and severe in 12 participants (3.1%) (Table 19). Regarding climbing stairs, 175 participants (45.7%)

reported no pain, 102 participants (26.6%) had very little pain, 69 participants (18%) had moderate pain, and 37 participants (9.7%) had severe pain (Table 20). Pain on descending stairs was absent in 209 participants (54.6%), very little in 87 participants (22.7%), moderate in 58 participants (15.1%), and severe in 29 participants (7.6%) (Table 21). When reaching up, 201 participants (52.5%) had no pain, 102 participants (26.6%) had very little pain, 54 participants (14.1%) had moderate pain, and 26 participants (6.8%) reported severe pain (Table 22). When bending over, 204 participants (53.3%) reported no pain, 111 participants (29%) had very little pain, 57 participants (14.9%) had moderate pain, and 11 participants (2.9%) reported severe pain (Table 23). Walking barefoot was pain-free in 238 participants (62.1%), very little painful in 86 participants (22.5%), moderate in 43 participants (11.2%), and severe in 16 participants (4.2%) (Table 24). Pain while standing after watching a movie was absent in 234 participants (61.1%), very little in 89 participants (23.2%), moderate in 46 participants (12%), and severe in 14 participants (3.7%) (Table 25). Pain while riding a bike was absent in 252 participants (65.8%), very little in 73 participants (19.1%), moderate in 41 participants (10.7%), and severe in 17 participants (4.4%) (Table 26). Running a short distance caused no pain in 207 participants (54%), very little in 98 participants (25.6%), moderate in 49 participants (12.8%), and severe in 29 participants (7.6%) (Table 27). Regarding the frequency of taking pain medicine, 289 participants (75.5%) took medicine less than once a week, 65 participants (17%) took it several times per week, 19 participants (5%) took it once daily, and 10 participants (2.6%) took it more than once every day since the injury (Table 28). The effect of medication was reported to always stop pain in 260 participants (67.9%), decrease pain in 69 participants (18%), usually take pain away in 24 participants (6.3%), and have little or no effect in 30 participants (7.8%) (Table 29). Pain had no emotional impact for 257 participants (67.1%), while it caused anxiety

in 72 participants (18.8%), daily worry in 38 participants (9.9%), and made 16 participants (4.2%) consider giving up activities (Table 30). Daily life activities were not limited for 267 participants (69.7%), but 96 participants (25.1%) avoided some activities, and 20 participants (5.2%) avoided all activities due to pain (Table 31). Hamstring tightness was mild (11-20) in 190 participants (49.6%), moderate (21-30) in 89 participants (23.2%), and severe (31-40) in 104 participants (27.2%) (Table 32). Finally, the total score showed 256 participants (66.8%) scored between 1-30, 118 participants (30.8%) scored between 31-60, and 9 participants (2.3%) scored between 60-100 (Table 33).

DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted to investigate the relationship between hamstring muscle tightness and plantar fasciitis among individuals aged 20 to 40 years. The results demonstrated a notable association between the two conditions, with the majority of participants who exhibited symptoms of plantar fasciitis also showing signs of hamstring tightness. These findings are consistent with previous literature suggesting that muscular imbalances in the posterior chain particularly involving the hamstrings may contribute to bio-mechanical stress on the plantar fascia, thereby increasing the risk or intensity of plantar heel pain.

In the current study, 49.6% of participants had mild hamstring tightness, 23.2% had moderate tightness, and 27.2% experienced severe hamstring tightness. A significant association was found between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis severity ($p < 0.001$), as reflected in the total score derived from the PFPS questionnaire. Participants with higher levels of hamstring tightness generally reported greater discomfort and limitations in daily activities such as walking, standing, climbing stairs, and performing other weight-bearing functions.

Additionally, the study revealed that plantar fasciitis was more prevalent among female

participants (57.4%) than males (42.6%), and this association between gender and plantar fasciitis severity was statistically significant ($p = 0.009$). These findings align with previous studies, including those by Kuo-Chang Sung et al. (2020) and Bhagyashree Koli et al. (2018), which found that women, especially those involved in occupations requiring prolonged standing or static postures, are at higher risk for developing plantar fasciitis.

Pain location and timing also supported the diagnosis. Most participants reported pain localized to the toes, mid-sole, and bottom of the heel—regions commonly affected in plantar fasciitis. Notably, a large number of participants experienced pain when first getting up in the morning or after prolonged sitting, which is consistent with classical clinical presentations of plantar fasciitis. Pain was often worse during weight-bearing tasks, such as walking, climbing stairs, or standing on the toes.

Chi-square analysis further revealed statistically significant associations between hamstring tightness and pain intensity during functional activities. For example, participants with tight hamstrings reported greater difficulty when standing on their toes, walking after waking up, or climbing stairs. These findings support the concept that hamstring tightness contributes to altered gait mechanics, thereby increasing strain on the plantar fascia during dynamic movement, a relationship echoed in studies by Labovitz et al. (2011) and Sayed et al. (2019).

Moreover, participants with higher levels of hamstring tightness experienced more difficulty in managing their pain and were more likely to report limitations in daily activities. This reflects the growing understanding in musculoskeletal and sports rehabilitation that tightness in one muscle group can lead to compensatory changes in movement and load distribution elsewhere in the body.

Interestingly, although most participants acknowledged experiencing pain, a majority reported that it was manageable. Around 64% described the pain as “easy to deal with,” and only a small fraction found it “almost

impossible” to cope with. This may suggest that while hamstring tightness can aggravate plantar fasciitis symptoms, many individuals adapt over time or have a relatively high pain threshold. Emotional impact was relatively low, with most participants reporting no significant psychological distress. However, some did report anxiety or frustration related to chronic discomfort, aligning with findings by Henriksen et al. (2012), who discussed emotional and bio-mechanical adaptations in individuals with chronic heel pain.

Overall, the data from this study not only reinforces existing literature but also provides fresh insights into the prevalence and functional consequences of hamstring tightness in individuals with plantar fasciitis, particularly in the local context of Pakistani physiotherapists and general population.

LIMITATIONS:

Following are the limitation of our study:

The cross-sectional nature of the research design limits the ability to draw causal inferences between hamstring tightness and plantar fasciitis.

The use of non-probability sampling may affect the generalize ability of the results to the broader population.

Furthermore, potential confounding variables, such as body mass index, footwear habits, occupational demands, and physical activity levels, were not fully controlled and may have influenced the outcomes.

Geographical limitation to local population as data was collected from Rawalpindi and Islamabad.

Time and resources constraints limited advanced diagnostics and longer followup.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Our study was conducted that aimed to check the prevalence of plantar fasciitis and its association with hamstring tightness. A significant amount of individuals with plantar fasciitis were found who had increased

hamstring tightness to confirm the association. These findings suggest that due to altered lower limb mechanics, increased strain is placed on plantar fascia leading to development of plantar fasciitis heel pain. Clinically, this association highlights importance of hamstring flexibility assessment and stretching exercises for muscle to prevent secondary complications as well as management of plantar fasciitis. Hence it is recommended to promote the importance of an active lifestyle with exercise on daily basis to prevent muscle tightness and development plantar fasciitis and other similar conditions. The authors of this study are hopeful that further research will be done on this subject to confirm the prevalence of plantar fasciitis and its association with hamstring tightness among general population. The purpose of this study was to check for prevalence of plantar fasciitis and its association with hamstring tightening. This association calls for general awareness among public regarding the impact of tight musculature on your daily lifestyle. It is recommended to instill basic knowledge among general public regarding the management and treatment of these conditions which are associated with muscle tightness and also recommend primary prevention strategies to avoid these problems.

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